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EXPLANATION AND RESEARCH OF THE PROBLEM OF CONCEPTUALIZATION AND CATEGORIZATION OF THE CONCEPTOSPHERE OF “MORALITY” IN THE UZBEKISTAN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. This article discusses the concepts of conceptualization and categorization in the Uzbek language, their essence, current research, and their role in linguistics. The article extensively and comprehensively studies the role of conceptualization and categorization in the expression and research of the concept of “morality”.

Key words: conceptosphere, conceptualization, category, concept, worldview, knowledge, morality, interpretation, categorization.

From the perspective of cognitive linguistics and cognitive psychology, conceptualization and categorization are closely related, but distinct cognitive processes. First, a person forms concepts about individual objects. Then, he combines similar concepts into a group, that is, a category. Thus, concepts are the lexical base necessary for the formation of categories.

Categories are a mechanism that organizes concepts and gives them a certain structure. For example, if the concept of “morality” is general, by dividing it into the above categories, we learn and clarify deeper knowledge about morality. Language plays a very important role in the formation of these lexical bases. Words serve as common meanings for concepts and categories, contributing to their formation and spiritual expansion. With the help of language, we share our concepts and categories with others, thereby creating common spiritual and social knowledge about our national culture.

In short, the human brain constantly performs conceptualization and categorization processes to understand and comprehend the world. Conceptualization results in the formation of identifiable mental units - concepts, while categorization combines these concepts into systematic groups - categories. These two processes are the basis of human cognitive abilities, which are further enhanced and interconnected through language.

He wrote about the relationship between language and thought and developed the idea that the system of categories of language determines the way a person perceives the world. This is directly related to the ability of the human mind to conceptualize phenomena. The process of conceptualization can be traced by analyzing the linguistic categories in his works. For example, the grammatical categories of a particular language reflect the way its speakers perceive and conceptualize the world.

In addition, categorization can also be considered a form of conceptualization, since categories are also concepts in their own right. Conceptualizing the world, that is, categorizing and dividing it into categories, is one of the important features of human thought.

As R.M. Frumkina noted, classification and categorization, although close to each other, differ in some aspects. Classification is the process of finding a generalizing word for a group of objects that have at least one common feature (for example, morality, justice, loyalty, conscience, faith - all of which are categories of spirituality). "By categorizing, a person organizes the world, and this order allows him to find, distinguish, and name objects in reality." The first studies on the internal structure of categories were conducted by the American psychologist E. Roche, and later became known as "prototype theory." In a broad sense, prototype theory is an approach aimed at studying the internal structure of concepts, some of whose elements are prototypes.

The purpose of this theory is to explain the correspondence of objects to prototypes within a specific interpretation of speech. Based on the structure and organizational features of the world, it can be said that orderliness is reflected in our knowledge in the form of various categories we choose. Systematicity is also present in the category itself, which distinguishes the central part - the core - and the peripheral sphere, that is, a set of members that are connected to the core to varying degrees. In the consciousness of a particular linguistic community, a prototype is an object of a category that has a “psychological difference”. As an example, for the Uzbek people, a prototype is the nation and the category of “personal morality”, “personal spirituality”.

The problem of categories is closely related to the problem of "concepts". Categories are formed around concepts, are included in them and are their "building material". Concepts, in turn, are formed in the process of human cognitive activity, that is, in the process of perceiving the environment. Thus, we come to the concept of a conceptual and linguistic representation of the world.

Conceptualization and categorization are cognitive processes that serve to systematize and generalize knowledge that arises as a result of human interaction with the environment. E.S. Kubryakov notes that although both of these processes are related to the structuring of knowledge, they differ in the final result and purpose of the activity. According to him, conceptualization is aimed at describing the minimum units of human experience in an ideal meaningful way, while categorization is aimed at combining units with similar properties into larger categories.

Categorization is the process of grouping similar concepts or objects into larger categories. This process results in the formation of categories or classes. Categorization helps to further systematize the knowledge generated by conceptualization. This process aims to generalize, simplify, and increase the efficiency of human knowledge. Similarity criteria and hierarchy play an important role in the categorization process. For example, the internal categories of the category

“Morals” are very important and are an important classification for the fields of cognitive linguistics and linguocultural studies. We will use the principles of similarity criteria and hierarchy to classify this category.

I. Category Fundamentals / Theoretical Foundations of morality:

I. Category “Defining moral and spiritual needs and norms”: This group reflects the most universal and subjective aspects of morality. It encompasses fundamental moral needs such as a person’s inner spiritual aspirations, conscience, sense of justice, and kindness, and the general norms that regulate them. This is the source and foundation of all other types of morality.

II. “Morality principles” category:

This section classifies the specific manifestations of ethical principles in various socio-cultural and professional spheres of society.

For example:

II. 1. Laws related to personal ethics and ensuring their implementation.

II. 2. Ethical norms (constitution) that regulate the behavior of an individual in a particular professional or organizational activity.

III. “Expressing professional ethic”s" category: (the “ethics” standards of each organization).

Each profession requires its own set of ethical rules (e.g., medical ethics, teaching ethics, legal ethics). These ethical standards define the specific characteristics of professional activities, the scope of responsibilities, and interactions with clients.

IV. “Expressing the Ethic of Service” category:

It is a sub-section or specific aspect of “professional ethics”. It focuses on aspects such as standards of behavior, honesty, courtesy, and professionalism in the process of serving customers and consumers.

V. “Ethics of Interpersonal and Social Relations” category:

Ethics are the rules that govern people's behavior in everyday life, family, community, and international relations.

VI. “A spiritual group of nouns expressing “family morality”:

Moral norms in family relationships (husband and wife, parent-child, brother and sister) include values such as loyalty, respect, responsibility, and mutual assistance.

VII. “A spiritual group of nouns expressing the ethics of diplomacy:

This is the highest, macro-social and international level of ethics. It includes principles such as the behavior of diplomats in interstate relations, negotiations, and international law, their communication protocols, and mutual respect and trust.

VIII. Ethics of the cultural and creative industries. This area includes the artistic expression, reflection, and analysis of moral principles. For example: the spiritual group of noun units “expressing the morality of literary fiction.” This group does not directly concern practical behavior, but rather concerns issues such as how moral values are reflected in works of art, the moral choices of characters, the moral impact of literature on society, and the moral responsibility of the writer and reader. This is a theoretical and aesthetic interpretation of morality.

In conclusion, this classification helps to understand the category of “Morals” in a comprehensive way. It includes everything from the universal foundations of morality to how it is applied to various social situations and even its artistic expression. This hierarchical structure shows the complexity of moral concepts and their interrelationships. Furthermore, these categories are further divided into smaller categories.

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